

How to Create an Artificial Thought and Intelligence? and the Math of Letters

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 19 April 2023	The construction of a thought and an artificial intelligence is possible with the language of numbered letters. Language that arose through the creation of the book "New mathematics of letters, triumph with mathematics" updated with the title "New mathematics of letters 2nd edition". Books that expose the language of letters and a mathematics of letters where addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of letters are found, with examples and their corresponding mathematical tables. With the mathematics of letters, any type of mathematical operations can be done, since it is one more mathematics. With the language of numbered letters in order, which represent letters, words and sentences numbered in order, a robot with artificial intelligence through the numbers of words numbered in order could acquire endless all kinds of information obtained by any artificial sense. Numeric information that would have to be transformed into binary numbers.
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INTRODUCTION

Why have I created the mathematics of numbered letters in order and a language of numbered letters in order that will allow an artificial intelligence to think by acquiring information numbered in order?: Because for many years I have a great hobby in creating new ideas about science, philosophy, crossword games, math games and sudoku games. Ideas that you can see in my 102 books published on Amazon.es and in my blogs: <http://sudokusycrucigramas.blogspot.com> <http://evolucioninteligentesinfin.com>, ideas that led me to create a math of letters using the 27 letters of the Spanish alphabet. Math of letters that I had to enumerate in order to create it more easily. From there was born the mathematics of the decimal system from 0 to 27 letters and a language of ordinarily numbered letters that you can see in my book "New Letter Mathematics 2nd Edition" published on Amazon. The language of numbered letters is ideal for artificial intelligence, since with numbered letters information could be obtained in the form of a number of everything known to which a name has been given. In this way, a robot could obtain information in the form of numbers from everything known to which a name has been given, and then be able to easily transform that number into binary numbers. Thus, and

by installing a complete dictionary of ordinarily numbered words, the robot could consult in the dictionary of numbered words the numerical information of the letters, words and numbered sentences obtained by its artificial senses, in order to know in number form the meanings of letters, words, and numbered sentences. Information that can be transformed into binary numbers and ordinary numbers as many times as necessary.

Human thought works in a similar way, transforming the information obtained by the five senses into binary numerical information related to positive and negative energies of all types of information, surely quantum-managed information, which will be taken to the great binary numerical mental dictionary stored in our thinking to consult the information obtained. This is thinking, and intelligence would be the way to handle information in the best possible way.

HOW TO CREATE AN ARTIFICIAL THOUGHT?

The order of the letters exposed in the commented books and their corresponding ordered numbering of the system from 0 to 27 letters of the Spanish alphabet, is an order in which, for example, the letters CASA will belong numerically to the word casa and not to another word, the letters PARROT will belong numerically to the word parrot and not to another

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word, and this will happen with all the letters and words that exist.

Humanity has given a name to almost everything we know, names that carry their corresponding letters so that we can understand what is known. By putting the letters their corresponding ordered numbers of the decimal system, according to the order exposed in the numbering of letters from 0 to 27 letters of the Spanish alphabet exposed in this book, a numerical way of being able to understand everything in the form of a number has been created. what has been named.

We understand what exists through words, thanks to the fact that our thoughts have memorized in an evolutionary way and in a binary way all kinds of information. Surely that binary way of handling the information that we memorize derives from the negative and the positive that everything has in the form of energy. In a binary way we transform two different types of information into a binary numerical type of storing the information, which we have transformed evolutionarily into an oral way of understanding the information; but the machines will not have the same mental development as us, they will have it better because they can be fitted with a means to understand what is known, such as the ordered numbering of the letters that I expose in those books, with which they will be able to memorize greater amounts of information and in a permanent way.

In these books I show the creation of a mathematics of letters with examples and tables corresponding to additions, subtractions, multiplications and divisions as well as a language of letters numbered in order that allows the information of everything known to what has been put a name do not lose their meanings in the form of numbered words.

Language of letters numbered in order that can be used for an artificial intelligence to acquire unlimited information and so that it can endlessly develop its artificial intelligence.

Although letter math is hard to learn because we are familiar with our decimal math, if it were learned it would be more fun math than number math. Furthermore, the mathematics of letters with fewer numbers of symbols encompasses more numbers of enumerations. Not having tried anything more than addition, subtraction, multiplication and division with their corresponding tables and examples.

Thanks to the creation of the mathematics of letters and having to enumerate them in order to facilitate their creation, I have created the language of numbered letters. Because of this, and since almost everything known has been given a name, everything that has a name acquires a numerical name. Like all computer science, it is based on binary numbers, which can be easily transformed into ordinary numbers and vice versa. By creating the numerical words of almost everything known, this numerical information can be easily handled with computer systems, with which, the language of numbered letters in order will be very important for artificial intelligence.

For the installation of the system of ordinarily numbered letters, not only would it be necessary to create a program with a large number of ordered enumerations of letters numbered in order with their corresponding transformations into binary numbers; It would also be necessary to make it possible for the information that a robot can obtain with any of its artificial senses, especially what is known to which a name has been given, to be transformed into binary form and in the form of letter numbers so that the robot knows the numbering in the form of letters that has everything known to which a name has been put.

If it detects new information that has not been named, this information would have to be brought into the program made up of a dictionary of words numbered in order with their corresponding numbered meanings; In order to find information that is as exact as possible to the information sought, and if said information is not found, it should be memorized as unknown information, this would form part of robotic learning. Transforming all the information obtained into binary information and you are able to transform them into numbers of the letters numbered in order whose numerical meanings correspond to the real meanings of the information obtained is the most suitable for an artificial intelligence to function as an artificial intelligence.

The robot would also have to install a dictionary of words numbered in order with their corresponding numerical meanings, that would not be difficult to do, it would be a matter of transforming from a dictionary all its words with their correct meanings into words numbered in order corresponding to the system of letters numbered in order, so that when the robot wants to consult information of any letter, word or sentence numbered in order, it has a numerical place where it can consult in the form of a number the meaning of any information it wishes to consult.

Our thinking acts in a similar way but with only binary information. In this way, by consulting a dictionary of words numbered in order, the robot could know in the form of a number transformed into a binary number what each information obtained means and then be able to transform that information enumerated into new ordinary numbers and into binary numbers. as many times as necessary for the best management of the information.

Through infinities of binary numerations obtained on the positive and negative energetics of the information obtained, linked to the infinities of memorized binary information on the negative and positive, is how our thought handles information. It is possible that human mental information is handled binary in a quantum way.

The most appropriate way to give robots a good handling of information would be to allow them to develop the information through words with their consequent numbered letters in order, and everything will be due to the fact that the letters have been numbered correctly, due to the creation of the mathematics of letters.

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Mathematics that could have been created without numbering but it would have been very difficult to create it. The numerical way in which the machines will be able to understand everything through the letters numbered in order, will also consist in the fact that the numbers of those letters can also be transformed into binary numbers and vice versa. And thanks to this, machines will be able to think in a similar way to how people think.

Upon discovering that with the enumerations of the letters the information of everything known to which a name has been given did not lose their meanings; I also discovered that this was very important for artificial intelligence, since with the proper installation of the numbered letters in order in a robot with artificial intelligence, it with its artificial senses could acquire information from everything and transform that information into binary numbers and then be able to transform them into numbers of the numbered letters in order. Since almost everything known has been given a name, artificial intelligence could understand the information of everything known in the form of words numbered in order. The information obtained by a robot with artificial intelligence would first have to be transformed into binary numbers, then converted into ordinary numbers corresponding to the numbering of the numbered letters in order to finally link each numbered word with similar numbered words contained in a dictionary of meanings of words numbered in order with the idea that the robot can understand in numbers the meaning of each information transformed into words numbered in order. Transforming that information obtained into a numerical way of understanding it, which is what our thinking does by handling information in a binary way; that is, handling information in a positive and negative way, whether it is information obtained through oral, visual, auditory, sensitive, olfactory or gustatory language. Through the letters and numbered words in order, the robot with artificial intelligence is provided with a more efficient means to transform information than the one we humans use mentally, since with this means the robot will be able to permanently memorize an infinite number of words, information and that would allow him to acquire unlimited wisdom. A robot that can acquire unlimited wisdom should not be a danger to society; since, through the appropriate programs, it could be forced to comply with the standards that we want.

When creating the mathematics of letters, I realized that the way we think consists of transforming the information that we acquire with any of our senses, into positive and negative binary numbers derived from the positive and negative that all information has. This system, logically, has evolved in humanity to allow us to have a large amount of memorization derived from positive and negative information.

The same system can be used to transmit the information, but in reverse.

If the robot did not find a copy of the information obtained that was as similar as possible in the dictionary of words numbered in order, then it would remain blank, more or less like we do when we do not understand something. Thus, comparing the information received with the information memorized is how people think.

In a similar way to how human thought has memorized information, in oral order and in order of importance, the robot should have it memorized. The more information the robot has memorized, the more complete its dictionary of memorized words will be, words that must have their corresponding numbered letters in order as shown in the mathematics of letters. The more complete this dictionary is, the more words it will have memorized with which the more words it will be able to compare.

If one of these robots obtained information from a cluster of single letters without meaning as a word, such as detecting the letters PFQT These letters, since they do not form something that is understood as a word, would not match the copy of memorized information, with which this information would be rejected since it does not exist as a copy of a word that is understood, only its individual letters would be understood. Therefore, this information would be information that could not be transformed into a binary form as a word, unless it is captured as single letter information.

The robot can be programmed in the language of your choice, as long as that language has been adapted to those programming and to the information that the robot has memorized.

Suppose that a robot were equipped with cameras to be able to see, and that all the information that it visually captures could internally transform it into binary information. Whether it is information about the shapes you see, as well as the distances and places where each captured image is located, as well as the colors, tones, degrees, etc., that is, visual captures as similar to how people see them. Not only the robotic brain, it would have to computerize everything it saw through the cameras into binary numbers, it would also have to drive the information in binary form and with computer speed to a place where it should be compared with the stored information. Thus, when the copy most similar to the information obtained is found, robotic thought will be able to know what it has seen.

The information captured with the other artificial senses will have a similar function, only that instead of being visual information it will be of another type. Logically, each sense will have its particular ways of obtaining information.

Everything is explained in a very superficial way, since it is presumable that human thought is much more complex than what is described, since the human being not only has to have memorized numerous copies in the form of images, but also has them memorized on auditory information, sensitive, olfactory and gustatory, which will also have their copies

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memorized orally, so that our thinking can understand this information orally.

Animals and plants have not developed the ability to memorize letters as we do, their memorizations are mainly based on inherited memorizations on survival issues.

Everything can be transformed into binary numbers starting from the smallest, since everything has its positive and its negative, that is, its pros and cons.

When we see something, the visual language transmits to us a mixture of visual positive and negative energy information that our brain will compare with the visual information that we have memorized, either inherited or from what we have learned, and this visual dictionary memorized binary is the one that will show us the visual information most similar to the one obtained. That way we know what we see; The information obtained by each sense will be treated in the same way, logically each sense has its own informative language, with which the information will be treated the same but depending on the information of each language.

Our thinking has not yet been able to evolve in such a way that we can memorize everything permanently, that is why we forget a lot of information, normally we tend to remember the most important information.

The robot that can acquire unlimited wisdom will have to be programmed a way to be able to hold it, in order to be able to handle it. Since it would be a very powerful machine, both physically and mentally; since in addition to having the ability to learn more and more, he would have the knowledge to be able to repair himself and be able to create increasingly sophisticated physical parts.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest

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